

Supplementary information for manuscript

Development of high-performance and cost-effective electrode assembly for redox flow battery

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Figure S1: a) Position of thermocouples in GF/BP/GF electrode assembly z-x view and in b) y-x view.

Figure S2: Scheme of apparatus for dry resistance measurement: 1) pistons of press, 2) PP plates, 3) composite plates, 4) electrode assembly.

Figure S3: Scheme of assemblies for dry resistance measurement and positioning of voltage and current sensing for each arrangement: 1. GF/BP arrangement, 2. GF/BP/GF arrangement, 3. CC/BP/GF arrangement. The sing plus (+) stand for unbonded components, and the dark red line represent position of connection.

Figure S4: a) Schematics of VRFB single cell. b) Schematics of experimental set-up for testing electrode assemblies consisting of VRFB single cell, OCV cell, tubing, diaphragm pumps and tanks. Green dash line represents membrane. c) Schematics of experimental for testing electrode assemblies set-up consisting of VRFB stack, OCV cell, tubing, peristaltic pumps and tanks. VRFB cell/stack and OCV cell obtained from Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o without GF and membranes.

Fig. S5. Scheme of equivalent circuit for evaluation of R_{Ω} and R_{CT} from EIS spectra. $R_{CT} = R_2 + R_3$. EC-lab fitting tool was used for fitting the EIS spectra. In manuscript all resistances are multiplied by geometric area of electrode (i.e. 50 cm^2) and thus referred as Area specific resistance ASR .

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

e)

Figure S6: Damages of BP occurred during the hot-pressing at too high temperature caused by over melting of BP: **a)** top site, **b)** bottom side. The figure b also represents decreased area in GF/BP connection. **c)** Additional photography of damage caused by insufficient length of cooling phase, i.e. elevated area in GF/BP connection. **d)** Half-cut through GF/BP electrode assembly shows effective bonding of GF. **e)** and **f)** Fibers of GF remaining in the structure of BP after ripping off the GF from GF/BP electrode assembly.

a)

Figure S7: Connecting copper current collector to create CC/BP/GF. **a)** manually disconnected Cu plate after connection. Bond between Cu plate GF was created, however on the right side, the disconnection was observed. Clear copper surface (green arrow) shows the area where the CC was effectively connected, the red arrow shows the area of the oxidized copper surface where the CC has been ripped off the BP due to excessive stress. **b)** CC/BP/GF electrode assembly with Cu foil effectively connected: left picture shows CC/BP/GF with cleaned Cu foil after connected and right one shows the oxidation of surface that occur on the side in contact with air of Cu foil at elevated temperatures. All the CCs were first cleaned as it looks on the left.

Table S1: Dry area specific resistance of RFB single-cell

Single-cell	$ASR_{\text{dry-cell}} / \Omega \text{ cm}^2$	CR / %
BP _{com.}	0.52	20
BP _{ext.}	2.1	20
GF/BP	0.86	10
CC/BP/GF	0.52	10

Figure S8: Area specific resistances of the VRFB single-cell: **a)** ASR_{Ω} (ohmic) in SoC -50%, +50% evaluated from EIS at the beginning (INT) and after experiment (AFT). **b)** ASR_{LC} in +50% SoC evaluated from load curves (charge and discharge). Dark colours are for the initial characterization and light colour for the after characterization. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm^{-3} vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min^{-1} , charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm^{-2} , voltage limits $0.8 \text{ V} - 1.65 \text{ V}$. Load curve measurement current density range $0 - 60 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

Figure S9: Area specific resistances of the VRFB single-cell experiments with GF2 comparing two different bonding methods: **a)** ASR_{Ω} (ohmic) in SoC -50%, +50% evaluated from EIS at the beginning (INT) and after experiment (AFT). **b)** ASR_{LC} in +50% SoC evaluated from load curves (charge and discharge). Dark colours are for the initial characterization and light colour for the after characterization. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm^{-3} vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min^{-1} , charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm^{-2} , voltage limits $0.8 \text{ V} - 1.65 \text{ V}$. Load curve measurement current density range $0 - 60 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

Figure S10: Area specific resistances of the VRFB stack experiments. **a)** ASR_{LC} area specific resistance per cell in SoC +50% evaluated from load curve measurements at the beginning (INT) and after experiment (AFT). **b)** ASR_{Ω} , ASR_{CT} , $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ area specific resistance per cell (ohmic, charge transfer and total, respectively) in SoC +50% evaluated from EIS. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm^{-3} vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 150 ml min^{-1} , charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm^{-2} , voltage limits $1.6 \text{ V} - 3.3 \text{ V}$. Load curve measurement current density range $0 - 60 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.